

TO15.isochron

Data at 1-sigma
Results at 2-sigma
Does not include error in J

Age = 4.58 ± 0.18 Ma (4.0%)
 $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{36}\text{Ar}$ Int. = 308 ± 12
MSWD = 0.99, P = 0.45, n = 13